

Tracing carbon exchanges/fluxes between Arctic and Atlantic basins

CarbEx

Data Management Plan

Disclaimer and acknowledgement

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Project abstract

Dissolved organic matter (DOM) consists of a complex mixture of molecules generated from the degradation of living organisms. Surface waters of the Arctic Ocean (AO) have high concentrations of DOM and freshwater (FW) due to the massive supply from large rivers. Great part of it is exported to the Atlantic Ocean through the Fram Strait (FS). Climate change is expected to increase riverine FW and terrestrial DOM supply, with consequences to the hydrological and carbon cycles. However, such changes remain poorly understood and CarbEx will contribute to rectifying this. The three central goals are to (1) estimate the DOM and FW fluxes from the Arctic to the Atlantic Ocean through the FS, (2) assess their variability and (3) develop an approach to assess the amount of both terrestrial DOM and FW, from optical measurements of DOM. A major challenge is to obtain sufficient data from the region and CarbEx will apply three complementary approaches: oceanographic expeditions (OE), ocean color remote sensing (OCRS, satellite-based Earth Observation) and numerical modelling (NM). Riverine FW and DOC fluxes will be estimated using a combination of observations and NM. Hydrographic and biogeochemical data acquired during a series of OE conducted annually in the FS (Summer 2009–2018) is available. The in situ data will be complemented with OCRS and NM to develop a continuous time series, filling the temporal coverage gaps from OE, to analyze possible trends and links to climate change in the Arctic. CarbEx also has a non-academic character and will provide the necessary foundation to develop new technologies to monitor the FW and carbon dynamics in the AO and aquaculture sites, i.e. in situ multi-channel fluorometers. This aligns with the host's strategy to develop observational technology and Arctic research, and with the EU's goal for the IF programme about stimulating the creative and innovative potential through advanced training and international and intersectoral mobility.

Project goal & objectives

The goal of this project is to employ spectroscopy measurements (e.g., absorption and fluorescence) and chemometrical data analysis combined to numerical modeling to assess and characterize the export of freshwater and dissolved organic matter (in terms of DOC) from the Arctic to the Atlantic Ocean through the Fram Strait with the following specific objectives:

- O1:** Develop a model for retrieving freshwater fractions from the optical properties of DOM.
- O2:** Determine the export of freshwater and riverine DOM from the Arctic to the Atlantic Ocean through the Fram Strait with numerical modelling.
- O3:** Evaluate the temporal variability of DOM and possible links to climate change with a merged time series composed by satellite data and the results from O1 and O2.

The results of this project will provide contemporary estimations of freshwater and DOC fluxes from the Arctic Ocean over a 10-year window, which is important for climate scientists improving climate models to understand how the Arctic ecosystem is changing. It is my hope that this project, along with generating a massive dataset on DOM and freshwater content and characterization, will shed light on the climate changes effects on the Arctic biogeochemistry, inspiring further research and large-scale funding on the topic.

1. DMP Philosophy

CarbEX defines “data” in the context of the MSCA-IF Contract, as “all digital outputs that are direct products of the research action”. As such, we aim for a Digital Output Management Plan, that applies FAIR Principles outlined below to all CarbEX digital outputs.

The CarbEX digital outputs will all be DOI-issued and centralized in Zenodo.org CarbEX Collection <https://zenodo.org/communities/carbex/>, and updated through version control.

The DMP first draft ([this version of the document](#)) will be updated at CarbEX milestone dates, to implement this philosophy to outputs beyond just experimental and field data.

2. Data Summary

What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?

Data collection from this project will allow me to answer the questions posed in the objectives of this project. In order to address the objectives, the collection of existing datasets, ocean color remote sensing and numerical simulations will be combined to fieldwork data collection.

What types and formats of data will the project generate/collect? CarbEx will combine three complementary approaches for monitoring the AO carbon export, particularly in the Fram Strait region: in situ sampling, ocean color satellite remote sensing and inverse modelling. The in situ dataset has already been collected and measured, and the data is available for the project. Numerical simulations will be validated with in situ data from the expeditions and velocity data from moorings deployed in the region. Finally, a merged dataset composed by ocean color remote sensing, in situ and numerical modelling results will be used to compose the time series to be analyzed in this project. The referred time series will be generated for the period between 2009-2018. All data generated in this project will be made available as text files (e.g., .txt and .csv). That format requires small storage capacity and can be easily converted to spreadsheets (e.g., .xlsx), which is generally sufficient for sharing or transfer of this type of data and are the formats most widely used in the community for data processing.

Will you re-use any existing data and how? I will likely take advantage of data that is already available from

the [Fram Strait Arctic OutFlow Observatory](#) run by the Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI), which hosts the long-term monitoring program at the Fram Strait and Greenland Sea. It consists of ten oceanographic expeditions conducted every August/September (from 2009 to 2018) in the Fram Strait and Greenland Sea. As the program continues to monitor the target regions, data from recent and upcoming expeditions will be integrated to the database as soon as available. Satellite data is freely available for download from the European Space Agency (ESA) through the [Ocean Colour-Climate Change Initiative \(OC-CCI\)](#).

What is the origin of the data? The data originates mainly from fieldwork campaigns conducted in the Fram Strait and Greenland Sea from 2009–2018. Satellite images are obtained through the OC-CCI Initiative. Simulations of freshwater transport are obtained with the [FEMSECT model](#).

What is the expected size of the data? The data that I will personally hold and manage from the project will occupy less than 50 GB, thus it should not pose challenges for sharing or transferring between users. Cloud storage programs such as Dropbox or Google Drive are generally sufficient for my data sharing needs.

To whom might it be useful ('data utility')? The data that I will generate may be useful for general circulation and earth system and ecosystem models.

3. FAIR data

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)? The data produced in this project will be published alongside the accompanying scientific publications. Some options are to deposit data in the [Norwegian Polar Data Centre](#) or [PANGAEA](#) where data publications are given a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) when published. As I have used PANGAEA several times before, I will most likely stick with this option. Another option for publishing larger scale oceanographic instrument profiles is to submit data to a larger oceanographic data repository such as [ICES data portal](#) or [NOAA's National Centers for Environmental Information](#).

What naming conventions do you follow? I will follow naming conventions and metadata standards outlined by the [Digital Curation Center](#) if applicable.

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use? Yes, most data repositories

function with keyword searches.

Do you provide clear version numbers? Yes, most data repositories allow for this and in the case that is necessary I will provide clear versions.

What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how. Metadata will be simple and describe the parameters measured, methodology employed for the analysis and their units. Any available standards will be used when reporting data.

3.2. Making data openly accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions. All data will be made openly available as a default.

Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if relevant provisions are made in the consortium agreement and are in line with the reasons for opting out. This does not apply in my case.

How will the data be made accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)? What methods or software tools are needed to access the data? Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included? Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)? As previously stated, data will be made available via repositories. I will submit data bases in .txt or .csv format, so that they can be read by most of the spreadsheet processing programs and converted easily into the formats necessary to each user and the software of their choice.

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible. As previously stated, data will be made available via repositories such as Norwegian Polar Data Centre or PANGAEA, both of which are open access.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository? If there are restrictions

on use, how will access be provided? Is there a need for a data access committee? Are there well described conditions for access (i.e. a machine readable license)? How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained? I have past experience with those repositories, which do not require prior arrangements, and there are no restrictions on use or access. The identity of the person accessing the data cannot be ascertained, though under the licensing agreement, proper attribution should be given when using the data.

3.3. Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)? Yes, data will be made interoperable.

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable? I have been unable to find standards for metadata vocabulary in my field. Thus, I will model my metadata vocabulary after similar research data in my field and provide enough information in the metadata.

Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow interdisciplinary interoperability? In the case that I find a standard vocabulary for my data and metadata, I will use it.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? I will, to the best of my abilities.

3.4. Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Data in the Norwegian Polar Data Centre and PANGAEA, for example, is often licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 and 3.0 Unported, respectively, where a user is free to share and adapt the data to his/her needs though appropriate credit must be given.

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible. Data should be made available for re-use after processing and quality control.

If an embargo should be necessary, it would be lifted soon after publication of the any scientific articles concerning the data in question.

Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why. Re-use of the data will not be restricted.

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable? Are data quality assurance processes described? Re-use of the data will be intended for the long-term. Data quality and details of the methodology behind data collection will be described in associated publications concerning the database and/or in the metadata itself.

4. Allocation of resources

What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project? I will likely use data repositories that are free of charge (e.g. Norwegian Polar Data Centre and PANGAEA).

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions). In the case I should have to cover the cost of publishing data, I will likely use my project funding to fund this.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project? I, Rafael Gonçalves Araujo, as the beneficiary of the grant will be responsible for data management in the project.

Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)? As the data from this project will be deposited in data repositories, they will be available in the long term, as the preservation is taken care of by the platform itself. Additionally, as corresponding author for the project publications, I will have my own versions of the data and can make it available on demand.

5. Data security

What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)? I use two back-up disks which are copied daily as well as the cloud systems from the University as well as Dropbox and Google Drive.

Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation? Not currently, but that is the end goal.

6. Ethical aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA). There are no relevant ethical or legal issues that will have an impact of data sharing in this project.

Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data? This is not applicable to this project.

7. Other issues

Do you make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones? I have used the platform [DMPonline](#) from the [Digital Curation Centre \(DCC\)](#), that is available for Danish research Institutions through the [Danish e-infrastructure Cooperation \(DeiC\)](#).

8. Operational map

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN			
Partner Legal Name	Project/GA No/WP	Researcher's name	email
Technical University of Denmark	CarbEx/ 839311	Rafael Gonçalves-Araujo	rafgo@aqua.dtu.dk
1. DATA SUMMARY			
Purpose of the Data	Purpose	Objectives	
	Gather information on the water chemistry in the Fram Strait region from data collected during expeditions and from satellite remote sensing	1. to develop a model for retrieving freshwater fractions from the optical properties of DOM 2. to determine the export of freshwater and riverine DOM from the Arctic to the Atlantic Ocean through the Fram Strait with numerical modelling 3. to evaluate the temporal variability of DOM and possible links to climate change with a merged time series composed by satellite data and the results from the other two objectives	
Type and Format of Data	Form	Format	Describe the type of data used or generated within the project, specifying the form and format of the data.
	Numeric	tables	.csv
Data Origin	Define and describe the origin/source of your data. Data can be gathered from different sources.		
Observational	Data collected during the expeditions and moored platforms in the Fram Strait from 2009-2018 as part of the Norwegian Polar Institute's Arctic Outflow Observatory. Data can be classified as hydrography (profiles of temperature, salinity and current velocity), water chemistry (concentration of dissolved organic carbon, dissolved inorganic nutrients concentrations, oxygen stable isotopes) and spectroscopic measurements (absorption and fluorescence spectra of colored dissolved organic matter)		
Derived/Compiled	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fluorescent dissolved organic matter components derived with Parallel Factor Analysis (PARAFAC) - Freshwater and Dissolved Organic Carbon exports in the Fram Strait - water fractions (Atlantic Water, Pacific Water, Meteoric Water, Sea Ice melt water) derived from water chemistry measurements - timeseries derived from Ocean Color Satellite Remote Sensing 		

Dataset is:	REVISABLE In situ data has already been collected and samples processed. However, more results from analysis will be added to the dataset during the project and some results might be removed after quality control.	
Quantity	Observational data Derived data	10 GB 5 GB
Data Security & Storage	Raw data are stored in the institute network drive; Intermediate data are stored in personal hard drives; Final, processed data are stored in the institute network drive.	Data is accessible to all project members
Data Value (long term)	Data are useful for distinct target audiences: dissolved organic matter community, Arctic physical and chemical oceanographers, earth system modelers. Additionally, the timeseries generated in this project can be used as a baseline for future monitoring of biogeochemical conditions in the changing Arctic Ocean.	
2 FAIR DATA		
2.1 FAIR DATA - Making data findable		
Discoverability of data (metadata provision)	All data will be published with the respective metadata. Metadata will include information on the sampling (geographic coordinates, date and instruments used to collect), samples/data processing (methodologies and treatment applied) and any other pertinent information regarding the data.	
Identifiability of data (refer to standard id mechanisms)	All data will be deposited in repositories and will have a DOI attributed to them. Those will be displayed in the respective scientific articles making use of the data.	
Naming conventions used	Data from different origins will be stored separately (e.g., observational/derived) and grouped according to their characteristics (e.g., spectra, timeseries, water chemistry, moored data, hydrography, PARAFAC components, etc.). The naming of the files will provide information enough to describe the file content.	
Search keywords approach	Appropriated keyword (following the standards of each research field) will be employed for indexing the data, so that all the outcomes can be easily find. Those will include date (year) and location of sampling, main parameters and methodology employed.	
Clear versioning approach	Different versions of the dataset will be accordingly displayed, with information on the date of release and changes from previous versions.	
2.2 Fair data Making data openly accessible		
Data openly available	Data will be deposited in the repositories as soon as processed and quality-controlled and will be granted a DOI, however with embargo, following the Norwegian Polar Institute's policy. Data will be made openly available at the time of publication of the respective scientific articles, which will display the link to access data.	
How data will be made available	Deposited in a repository (e.g., Norwegian Polar Data Centre , PANGAEA , etc.).	
Methods or software (SW) tools for data access	All data will be stored as tables in .csv format, that is a plain text and implies in no restriction to access the data with regards to the software available for the user.	
SW documentation and other information needed	There is no need for specific SW to access the data. All documentation needed to understand the data (i.e. abbreviations, supplementary notes) will be available in the metadata.	

Repository for deposit of data, metadata, documentation and code	Data will be deposited in an open repository (e.g., Norwegian Polar Data Centre , PANGAEA , etc.).
Access restrictions	After the publication of the respective scientific articles, data will be freely available with no restrictions. Before that, there will be an embargo to access the data, that will be made available only for the project researchers and journal editor and referees.
Data interoperability assessment	Vocabularies, standards and methodology information will be provided in the metadata. Naming and standards will follow the ones adopted by the respective scientific communities and it will be described in the metadata and scientific articles generated from the datasets.
2.3 Fair data Making data interoperable	
Standard vocabulary or mapping to commonly used ontologies	Vocabularies, standards and methodology information will be provided in the metadata. Naming and standards will follow the ones adopted by the respective scientific communities and it will be described in the metadata and scientific articles generated from the datasets.
2.4 FAIR DATA – Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses)	
Timing of data availability for re-use (incl. indications on embargo)	Data will be deposited in data repositories as soon as they are in their final format. There will be an embargo until publication of the scientific articles using the data. During the embargo, only project participants and journal editors and referees will be granted access. With the publication of the articles, data will be promptly available from the DOI presented in the respective articles.
Data usability by Third Parties (after the end of the project)	Data will be publicly available, and no restrictions apply. Users are requested to cite the dataset accordingly.
Restrictions to data re-use	No restrictions apply. Users are requested to cite the dataset accordingly.
Quality assurance process	Only quality-controlled data will be made available and data will be flagged accordingly.
Length of time of data re-usability	Does not apply.
3 ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES	
Costs estimates for making data FAIR	Making the project's data FAIR is already accounted in the project budget and there will be no extras costs related to that.
Data Management Responsibilities	The project's PI is responsible for data management in this project.